

Enhancing Cabbage Productivity Using Foliar-Applied Liquid Inorganic Fertilizer: A Dose-Response Study

Hafith Furqoni¹

¹Department of Agronomy and Horticulture, Faculty of Agriculture, Bogor Agricultural University, Jalan Meranti
Kampus IPB Dramaga, Bogor, Indonesia 16680

*Corresponding Author: hafithfurqoni@apps.ipb.ac.id

ABSTRACT

*Fertilization is essential for sustaining crop productivity, yet foliar application of NPK fertilizer remains underutilized in cabbage (*Brassica oleracea*) cultivation. This study evaluated the effectiveness of liquid inorganic NPK fertilizer applied directly to cabbage leaves to enhance growth and yield. The experiment followed a randomized complete block design (RCBD) with six treatments: no fertilizer (P0), 0.5 dose (P1), 0.75 dose (P2), 1.0 dose (P3), 1.25 dose (P4), and 1.5 dose (P5), alongside a uniform basal application of Urea, KCl, and SP-36. Results showed that the 1.5-dose treatment significantly improved plant height, leaf number, yield per plot, and yield per hectare compared to the control. Economically, this treatment also achieved the highest benefit-cost ratio, indicating superior profitability. These findings suggest that foliar application of liquid inorganic fertilizer is both agronomically effective and economically viable for cabbage production. The recommended application rate is 3.0 L/ha, applied at 2, 3, 4, and 5 weeks after transplanting.*

Keywords: benefit-cost analysis, cabbage growth and yield, foliar fertilization, liquid inorganic NPK, macronutrient uptake

INTRODUCTION

Fertilization is a cornerstone of modern agriculture, essential for maintaining soil fertility and ensuring that crops receive the nutrients necessary for optimal growth and productivity. The combined use of organic and inorganic fertilizers enables the delivery of vital macro- and micronutrients while also enhancing soil structure and promoting beneficial microbial activity (Mahmood et al., 2017; Manzoor et al., 2024). Organic fertilizers contribute to long-term soil health by increasing organic matter and improving nutrient cycling (Alcántara et al., 2016; Herencia et al., 2008), whereas inorganic fertilizers offer rapid nutrient availability and support key physiological functions such as photosynthesis and enzymatic activity (Miao et al., 2011). When applied in a balanced manner, these fertilizers can significantly improve crop yields and soil quality, particularly in rotational systems like rice–oilseed rape (Yousaf et al., 2017). The emergence of precision agriculture has further enhanced nutrient management by enabling targeted application, thereby reducing environmental risks such as nutrient runoff and soil degradation (Ameyu, 2024).

Among macronutrients, nitrogen (N), phosphorus (P), and potassium (K) are fundamental to plant development. Nitrogen is especially critical due to its role in photosynthesis, respiration, and the synthesis of amino acids and chlorophyll (Dell'Acqua et al., 2024; Perkowski et al., 2024; Yao et al., 2023). Although nitrogen is abundant in the atmosphere, plants can only absorb it in the form of ammonium (NH_4^+) and nitrate (NO_3^-) through their roots (Kuppe & Postma, 2024; Fallahi & Sharifi, 2020; Zi et al., 2025). Nitrogen uptake is dynamic, peaking during early growth stages and declining as plants mature, regulated by molecular mechanisms that adjust transporter expression to match developmental needs (Chen et al., 2024; Tulloss & Cadenasso, 2016; Khan et al., 2019). Efficient nitrogen use is further influenced by soil conditions and microbial interactions, with innovations such as biological nitrification inhibitors showing promise in enhancing ammonium uptake (Siqueira et al., 2020; Tanaka & Nakano, 2019; Weber et al., 2021).

Potassium also plays a vital role in plant physiology, particularly in protein synthesis, by activating enzymes involved in nitrogen metabolism (Wang et al., 2018). A deficiency in K has been linked to reduced nitrate and soluble protein levels, as well as impaired enzymatic activity, which negatively affects protein synthesis (Xu et al., 2022; Tahir et al., 2023). Additionally, K helps regulate ionic balance and supports metabolic homeostasis during periods of active growth. Phosphorus complements these functions by participating in cell division, respiration, and root development. Absorbed as phosphate ions, P is a structural and regulatory component of nucleic acids and energy molecules such as ATP and ADP, facilitating energy transfer and supporting cellular metabolism (Wang et al., 2024).

Despite the importance of these nutrients, foliar application of NPK fertilizer remains underutilized in cabbage (*Brassica oleracea*) cultivation. Given its potential to enhance nutrient uptake efficiency and crop performance, this study aims to evaluate the effectiveness of liquid inorganic NPK fertilizer applied directly to cabbage leaves, with the goal of optimizing growth and yield.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Materials

The materials used in this experiment included cabbage seeds, liquid inorganic fertilizer, Urea, SP-36, and KCl. The tools utilized comprised standard cultivation equipment such as hoes, hand forks, sprayers, sample markers, measuring tapes, and digital scales. Data analysis was performed using a computer equipped with the SAS statistical software. The liquid inorganic fertilizer contained 5.38% nitrogen (N), 4.60% phosphorus pentoxide (P_2O_5), and 5.70% potassium oxide (K_2O).

Methods

The experiment was arranged in a randomized complete block design (RCBD). The treatments consisted of six levels of liquid inorganic fertilizer application: no fertilizer (P0), 0.5 dose (P1), 0.75 dose (P2), 1.0 dose (P3), 1.25 dose (P4), and 1.5 dose (P5). Each treatment was replicated four times, resulting in a total of 24 experimental units. Each unit was a plot measuring 25 m². All plots received a basal fertilizer application of 200 kg/ha Urea, 100 kg/ha KCl, and 100 kg/ha SP-36. Details of the treatments are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Details of Liquid Inorganic Fertilizer Treatments

Treatment	Concentration (ml/liter water/application)	Dosage (L/ha/application)
Control	-	-
0.5 dose of liquid inorganic fertilizer	2	1
0.75 dose of liquid inorganic fertilizer	3	1.5
1.0 dose of liquid inorganic fertilizer	4	2
1.25 dose of liquid inorganic fertilizer	5	2.5
1.5 dose of liquid inorganic fertilizer	6	3

Field Preparation and Crop Management

The field was thoroughly prepared by double-tilling with a hoe until it was ready for planting. The second tillage was followed by the construction of raised beds, each measuring 1 meter in width and 5 meters in length, with approximately 50 cm spacing between beds. Each experimental unit consisted of five raised beds, each 5 meters long.

Seedlings were transplanted at 21 days after sowing, with one seedling per planting hole. The planting spacing used was 60 cm × 40 cm, with one plant per hole. Fertilization was carried out according to local recommendations. The liquid inorganic fertilizer was applied at the designated treatment doses during the 2nd, 3rd, 4th, and 5th weeks after transplanting (WAT). Basal fertilizers, Urea, SP-36, and KCl were applied at 1 WAT. Pest and disease control was conducted as needed, based on the severity of infestation, using pesticides in a limited and targeted manner.

Data Collection

Plant growth observations included measurements of plant height and the number of leaves. These observations were conducted on five randomly selected sample plants within each experimental unit. Yield and yield components were assessed by measuring yield per plant, yield per plot, and extrapolated yield per hectare, which was calculated based on the plot-level data.

Statistical Analysis and Economic Evaluation

The data were statistically analyzed using analysis of variance (ANOVA), followed by Duncan's Multiple Range Test (DMRT) at a 5% significance level to determine differences among treatment means. A farm business analysis was conducted using economic evaluation parameters, including profit and the benefit-cost ratio (B/C).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Results

Effect of Liquid Inorganic Fertilizer on Cabbage Plant Growth

The application of liquid inorganic fertilizer had a significant effect on cabbage plant height (Table 2). Plants treated with the fertilizer exhibited greater height compared to the control. Treatments with 0.5 to 1.5 doses of liquid inorganic fertilizer resulted in improved plant height from 3 to 6 weeks after transplanting (WAT). At 6 WAT, plant height ranged from 39.5 to 41.8 cm in the fertilizer-treated plots, whereas the control treatment produced a height of only 34.7 cm. Although the fertilizer treatments enhanced plant growth compared to the control, there were no statistically significant differences in plant height among the different fertilizer dose levels.

Table 2. Effect of Liquid Inorganic Fertilizer Application on Cabbage Plant Height

Treatment	Plant Height (cm)			
	3 WAT	4 WAT	5 WAT	6 WAT
Control	14.7b	20.9b	28.2b	34.7b
0.5 dose of liquid inorganic fertilizer	18.8a	25.8a	34.5a	39.6a
0.75 dose of liquid inorganic fertilizer	19.4a	27.1a	33.6a	41.8a
1.0 dose of liquid inorganic fertilizer	18.7a	25.6a	32.7a	39.5a
1.25 dose of liquid inorganic fertilizer	19.3a	26.5a	33.5a	40.7a
1.5 dose of liquid inorganic fertilizer	18.7a	26.3a	34.6a	40.1a

Note: Values in the same column followed by the same letter are not significantly different according to Duncan's Multiple Range Test (DMRT) at the 5% significance level.

The application of liquid inorganic fertilizer significantly affected the number of leaves produced by cabbage plants (Table 3). Fertilizer treatments resulted in a higher leaf count compared to the control. Applications ranging from 0.5 to 1.5 doses of liquid inorganic fertilizer consistently produced more leaves from 3 to 6 weeks after

transplanting (WAT) than the control treatment. At 6 WAT, the number of leaves in the fertilizer-treated plants ranged from 12.5 to 12.7, while the control treatment produced only 10 leaves. However, there were no statistically significant differences in leaf number among the various fertilizer dose levels.

Table 3. Effect of Liquid Inorganic Fertilizer Application on Leaf Number of Cabbage Plants

Treatment	Leaf Number			
	3 WAT	4 WAT	5 WAT	6 WAT
Control	4.4b	5.9b	7.7b	10.0b
0.5 dose of liquid inorganic fertilizer	5.3a	7.4a	10.1a	12.6a
0.75 dose of liquid inorganic fertilizer	5.3a	7.4a	10.1a	12.5a
1.0 dose of liquid inorganic fertilizer	5.3a	7.3a	9.9a	12.5a
1.25 dose of liquid inorganic fertilizer	5.6a	7.7a	10.2a	12.5a
1.5 dose of liquid inorganic fertilizer	5.5a	7.5a	10.1a	12.7a

Note: Values in the same column followed by the same letter are not significantly different according to Duncan's Multiple Range Test (DMRT) at the 5% significance level.

Effect of Liquid Inorganic Fertilizer on Cabbage Yield

The application of liquid inorganic fertilizer significantly affected yield per plot and yield per hectare, but had no significant effect on yield per plant (Table 4). Differences in fertilizer dose levels did not result in significant changes in yield per plant between treatments and the control. However, the application of 1.5 doses of liquid inorganic fertilizer produced the highest yield per plot at 41.0 kg, compared to only 34.7 kg in the control. This trend was consistent with the yield per hectare, where the 1.5-dose treatment resulted in a yield of 16.4 tons/ha, while the control yielded only 13.9 tons/ha. The application of 1.5 doses of liquid inorganic fertilizer increased yield per hectare by 15.5% compared to the control.

Table 4. Effect of Liquid Inorganic Fertilizer Application on Cabbage Yield

Treatment	Yield/ Plant (g)	Yield/ Plot (kg)	Yield/ ha (kg/ha)
Control	133.3a	34.7b	13866.7b
0.5 dose of liquid inorganic fertilizer	148.7a	37.7ab	15066.7ab
0.75 dose of liquid inorganic fertilizer	164.0a	36.3ab	14533.3ab
1.0 dose of liquid inorganic fertilizer	154.7a	38.7ab	15466.7ab
1.25 dose of liquid inorganic fertilizer	150.7a	38.0ab	15200.0ab
1.5 dose of liquid inorganic fertilizer	146.7a	41.0a	16400.0a

Note: Values in the same column followed by the same letter are not significantly different according to Duncan's Multiple Range Test (DMRT) at the 5% significance level.

Farm Business Analysis

The economic effectiveness of liquid inorganic fertilizer was evaluated using profit and the benefit-cost ratio (B/C). These two indicators were used to assess the economic

feasibility of cabbage farming. The results of the farm business analysis for several treatments in the fertilizer effectiveness trial are presented in Table 5. All levels of liquid inorganic fertilizer application were economically effective, as indicated by positive profit values and B/C ratios greater than 1. The application of 1.5 doses of liquid inorganic fertilizer yielded the highest B/C ratio of 2.67, while the control treatment resulted in a B/C ratio of only 2.43.

Table 5. Results of Farm Business Analysis for Liquid Inorganic Fertilizer Treatments

Treatment	Cost (Rp)	Revenue (Rp)	Benefit (Rp)	B/C
Control	11,435,000	27,733,400	16,298,400	2.43
0.5 dose of liquid inorganic fertilizer	11,715,000	30,133,400	18,418,400	2.57
0.75 dose of liquid inorganic fertilizer	11,855,000	29,066,600	17,211,600	2.45
1.0 dose of liquid inorganic fertilizer	11,995,000	30,933,400	18,938,400	2.58
1.25 dose of liquid inorganic fertilizer	12,135,000	30,400,000	18,265,000	2.51
1.5 dose of liquid inorganic fertilizer	12,275,000	32,800,000	20,525,000	2.67

Discussion

This study demonstrates the positive impact of foliar application of liquid inorganic fertilizer on cabbage growth and yield. Applying doses ranging from 0.5 to 1.5 times the recommended amount resulted in significant improvements in plant height, leaf number, and overall productivity. The 1.5-dose treatment was particularly effective, increasing plant height by up to 17% and yield per hectare by 15.5% compared to untreated plants. Given that cabbage is a leafy crop, these enhancements in vegetative growth directly contribute to higher yields, making foliar fertilization a promising strategy for improving crop performance.

The success of foliar fertilization lies in its ability to deliver essential macronutrients—nitrogen (N), phosphorus (P), and potassium (K)—directly to the leaves, where they are rapidly absorbed and utilized (Sefano, 2025). Nitrogen, primarily taken up as nitrate (NO_3^-) and ammonium (NH_4^+), is crucial for synthesizing proteins, amino acids, nucleic acids, and chlorophyll, all of which are vital for healthy plant development (Gupta et al., 2024). Phosphorus, absorbed as H_2PO_4^- or HPO_4^{2-} , depending on soil pH, supports reproductive growth, root development, and crop quality, contributing to earlier maturity and improved nutrient uptake (Saha et al., 2022; Khan et al., 2006).

Potassium plays a key role in maintaining cellular integrity, regulating water balance, and enhancing resistance to pests and diseases. It also supports carbohydrate metabolism and protein synthesis, helping plants perform better under stress conditions (Kausar, 2016). However, potassium uptake can be affected by nutrient interactions—excess levels of NH_4^+ or Mg^{2+} may inhibit its absorption, potentially disrupting nutrient balance and metabolic efficiency (Chakwizira et al., 2025). These physiological insights emphasize the importance of balanced nutrient management when applying foliar fertilizers.

Beyond the biological benefits, the economic analysis further supports the value of this approach. The 1.5-dose treatment not only delivered the best agronomic outcomes but also achieved the highest benefit-cost (B/C) ratio, indicating strong economic viability. These findings suggest that integrating foliar NPK application into cabbage farming offers a practical and profitable solution for growers seeking to enhance both yield and resource efficiency.

CONCLUSION

The results of this study demonstrate that the application of 1.5 doses of liquid inorganic fertilizer significantly improves cabbage growth and yield. Specifically, it increases plant height, the number of leaves per plant, yield per plot, and yield per hectare compared to the control. Agronomically, the 1.5-dose treatment is effective, and economically, it is more profitable than the control. The findings confirm that liquid inorganic fertilizer is economically beneficial for cabbage cultivation. Based on this research, the recommended dose for cabbage is 3.0 L/ha per application, applied at 2, 3, 4, and 5 weeks after transplanting (WAT).

REFERENCES

- Ameyu, T. (2024). Response of Food Barley and Bread Wheat to the Application of Lime, Inorganic and Organic Fertilizer on Acidic Nitisols of West Shewa Zone, Ethiopia. *Middle East J Islam Stud Cult.*, 4(1): 1-8.
- Chakwizira, E., Andrews, M., Teixeira, E., & Moot, D. (2025). Effects of Elevated Atmospheric CO₂ Concentration on Growth, Grain Yield and Grain Macronutrient Concentrations of Wheat Under Different K Supply. *Journal of Plant Nutrition and Soil Science*, 188(3), 473-481.
- Chen, L. H., Xu, M., Cheng, Z., & Yang, L. T. (2024). Effects of nitrogen deficiency on the photosynthesis, chlorophyll a fluorescence, antioxidant system, and sulfur compounds in *Oryza sativa*. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences*, 25(19), 10409.
- Cvelbar Weber, N., Koron, D., Jakopič, J., Veberič, R., Hudina, M., & Baša Česnik, H. (2021). Influence of nitrogen, calcium and nano-fertilizer on strawberry (*Fragaria × ananassa* Duch.) fruit inner and outer quality. *Agronomy*, 11(5), 997.
- Dell'Acqua, N., Gambetta, G. A., Comont, G., Ferrer, N., Rochepeau, A., Pétriacq, P., & Delmas, C. E. (2025). Nitrogen nutrition impacts grapevine esca leaf symptom incidence, physiology, and metabolism. *Journal of Experimental Botany*, eraf172.
- Fallahi, S., & Sharifi, P. (2020). Effect of nitrogen fixing bacteria and nitrogen rate on yield and growth of common bean. *Acta Univ Agric Silv Mendel Brun*, 68, 491-496.
- Gupta, Ritika, Jay Nath Patel, and Mohd Shah Alam. (2024). Effect of Integrated Nutrient Management on Nutrient Content and Their Uptake by Soybean Crop (*Glycine Max L.*). *Journal of Scientific Research and Reports*, 30(7):1021-1032.

- Herencia, J. F., Ruiz, J. C., Melero, S., Galavís, P. G., & Maqueda, C. (2008). A short-term comparison of organic v. conventional agriculture in a silty loam soil using two organic amendments. *The Journal of Agricultural Science*, 146(6), 677-687.
- Kausar, A., Ashraf, M. Y., Gull, M., Ghafoor, R., Ilyas, M., Zafar, S., ... & Aftab, K. (2016). Alleviation of salt stress by K₂SO₄ in two wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.) cultivars. *Appl Ecol Environ Res*, 14(5), 137-147.
- Khan, F. U., Jhon, A. Q., Khan, F. A., & Mir, M. M. (2006). Effect of NPK and Zn on growth, flowering and bulb production in tulip under polyhouse conditions in Kashmir. *Journal of Horticultural Sciences*, 1(2), 129-134.
- Khan, S., Yu, H., Li, Q., Gao, Y., Sallam, B. N., Wang, H., ... & Jiang, W. (2019). Exogenous application of amino acids improves the growth and yield of lettuce by enhancing photosynthetic assimilation and nutrient availability. *Agronomy*, 9(5), 266.
- Kuppe, C. W., & Postma, J. A. (2024). Benefits and limits of biological nitrification inhibitors for plant nitrogen uptake and the environment. *Scientific reports*, 14(1), 15027.
- Li, Z., Li, Z., Lu, Y., Ren, B., Zeng, F., Yang, S., ... & Li, L. (2025). Overexpression of DWF1 Enhances Low-Nitrogen Stress Tolerance in Potato Plants. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences*, 26(9), 4374.
- Mahmood, F., Khan, I., Ashraf, U., Shahzad, T., Hussain, S., Shahid, M., ... & Ullah, S. (2017). Effects of organic and inorganic manures on maize and their residual impact on soil physico-chemical properties. *Journal of soil science and plant nutrition*, 17(1), 22-32.
- Manzoor, Ma, L., Ni, K., & Ruan, J. (2024). Influence of Organic and Inorganic Fertilizers on Tea Growth and Quality and Soil Properties of Tea Orchards' Top Rhizosphere Soil. *Plants*, 13(2), 207.
- Martínez-Alcántara, B., Martínez-Cuenca, M. R., Bermejo, A., Legaz, F., & Quinones, A. (2016). Liquid organic fertilizers for sustainable agriculture: Nutrient uptake of organic versus mineral fertilizers in citrus trees. *PloS one*, 11(10), e0161619.
- Miao, Y., Stewart, B. A., & Zhang, F. (2011). Long-term experiments for sustainable nutrient management in China. A review. *Agronomy for Sustainable Development*, 31, 397-414.
- Mndzebele, B., Ncube, B., Fessehazion, M., Mabhaudhi, T., Amoo, S., du Plooy, C., ... & Modi, A. (2020). Effects of cowpea-amaranth intercropping and fertiliser application on soil phosphatase activities, available soil phosphorus, and crop growth response. *Agronomy*, 10(1), 79.
- Niu, Z., An, F., Su, Y., Liu, T., Yang, R., Du, Z., & Chen, S. (2022). Effect of long-term fertilization on aggregate size distribution and nutrient accumulation in aeolian sandy soil. *Plants*, 11(7), 909.

- Perkowski, E. A., Terrones, J., German, H. L., & Smith, N. G. (2024). Symbiotic nitrogen fixation reduces belowground biomass carbon costs of nitrogen acquisition under low, but not high, nitrogen availability. *AoB Plants*, 16(5), plae051.
- Saha, P., Bohra, J. S., Mahapatra, D., Nayak, H., Singh, T., & Barman, A. (2022). Assessment of nutrient dynamics of diversified rice-wheat cropping sequences under integrated farming system of middle Igp. *Bangladesh Journal of Botany*, 51(3), 607-613.
- Sefano, M. A., Juniarti, & Gusnidar. (2024). Land Suitability Evaluation For Okra (*Abelmoschus esculentus* L.) In Nagari Nanggalo, Koto XI Tarusan District, Pesisir Selatan Regency, Indonesia Using GIS-AHP Technique. *International Journal of the Analytic Hierarchy Process*, 16(2). <https://doi.org/10.13033/ijahp.v16i2.1246>
- Sefano, M. A. (2025). Respon Tanaman Kedelai (*Glycine max* L.) Terhadap Lama Inkubasi Kapur Dolomit Pada Ultisol. *Journal Arunasita*, 2(1), 14-20.
- Sefano, M. A. (2025). Pertanian Berkelanjutan Berbasis AHP dan Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis: Sebuah Tinjauan Kritis. *Journal Arunasita*, 2(1), 21-34.
- Siqueira, R., Longchamps, L., Dahal, S., & Khosla, R. (2020). Use of fluorescence sensing to detect nitrogen and potassium variability in maize. *Remote Sensing*, 12(11), 1752.
- Tahir, M. A., Sabah, N., Warraich, M. W., Sarwar, G., Aftab, M., Mujeeb, F., ... & Hussain, S. (2023). Role of carbon sequestering and commercial fertilizers for minimizing bio available k losses using wheat as test crop under aridisols. *Pakistan Journal of Agricultural Research*, 36(3), 270-276.
- Tanaka, R., & Nakano, H. (2019). Barley yield response to nitrogen application under different weather conditions. *Scientific Reports*, 9(1), 8477.
- Tulloss, E. M., & Cadenasso, M. L. (2016). The effect of nitrogen deposition on plant performance and community structure: is it life stage specific?. *PloS one*, 11(6), e0156685.
- Wang, X., Hao, L., Zhu, B., & Jiang, Z. (2018). Plant calcium signaling in response to potassium deficiency. *International journal of molecular sciences*, 19(11), 3456.
- Xu, X., Wang, F., Xing, Y., Liu, J., Lv, M., Meng, H., ... & Jiang, Y. (2022). Appropriate and constant potassium supply promotes the growth of M9T337 apple rootstocks by regulating endogenous hormones and carbon and nitrogen metabolism. *Frontiers in Plant Science*, 13, 827478.
- Yao, X., Li, H., Nie, J., Liu, H., Guo, Y., Lv, L., ... & Sui, X. (2023). Disruption of the amino acid transporter CsAAP2 inhibits auxin-mediated root development in cucumber. *New Phytologist*, 239(2), 639-659.
- Yousaf, M., Li, J., Lu, J., Ren, T., Cong, R., Fahad, S., & Li, X. (2017). Effects of fertilization on crop production and nutrient-supplying capacity under rice-oilseed rape rotation system. *Scientific reports*, 7(1), 1270.